

Making photocatalysis comparable using a modular and characterized Open-Source photoreactor

(Supporting Information)

Daniel Kowalczyk^a, Pengcheng Li^a, Amir Abbas^b, Jonas Eichhorn^c, Philipp Buday^d, Magdalena Heiland^b, Andrea Pannwitz^b, Felix Schacher^c, Wolfgang Weigand^d, Carsten Streb^b, Dirk Ziegenbalg^{a*}

^aInstitute of Chemical Engineering, Ulm University, Albert-Einstein-Allee 11, 89081 Ulm, Germany,

^bInstitute of Inorganic Chemistry, Ulm University, Albert-Einstein-Allee 11, 89081 Ulm, Germany

^cInstitute of Organic Chemistry and Macromolecular Chemistry, University of Jena, Lessingstr. 8, 07743 Jena, Germany

^dInstitute for Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, University of Jena, Humboldtstr. 8, 07743 Jena, Germany

Table of Contents

Materials and Methods.....	3
Reagents and Instruments	3
Experimental Setups	3
Characterized LEDs.....	4
Photocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution Catalysis.....	5
[Mo ₃ S ₁₃] catalyzed hydrogen evolution	5
Synthesis of (NH ₄) ₂ [Mo ₃ S ₁₃] x 2H ₂ O.....	5
Synthesis of Na ₂ [Mo ₃ S ₁₃] x 5H ₂ O	5
Sample preparation and photocatalysis with low methanol ratio.....	5
Sample preparation and photocatalysis with high methanol ratio	6
Co(dm _g) ₂ CIPy catalyzed hydrogen evolution.....	6
Sample preparation and photocatalysis	6
Photonic Characterization.....	6
Chemical Actinometry.....	7
Radiometry	7
Calibration of the Radiometric Setup for the 365 nm LED (LST1-01G01-UV01-00).....	7
Calibration of the Radiometric Setup for the 455 nm LED (LST1-01F06-RYL1-00)	9
Calibration of the Radiometric Setup for the 460 nm LED (LZ1-00DB00 Dental Blue)	10
Calibration of the Radiometric Setup for the 453 nm LED (LZ4-40B208-0000)	11
Determination of the absorbed photon flux for the 365 nm LED (LST1-01G01-UV01-00).....	12
Photon Fluxes for the Experimental Setups used for Case Studies	16
Wavelength Dependent Reflective Properties of the Reactor Material.....	18

Materials and Methods

Reagents and Instruments

Reagents and solvents:

Tris(2,2'-bipyridine)ruthenium(II) hexafluorophosphate (97 %), L-ascorbic acid (99 %), [Co(dmg)₂ClPy] (100 %) and *N,N*-Dimethyl-*p*-toluidine (99 %) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Methanol (≥99.8 %) was purchased from VWR International GmbH, *N,N*-dimethylformamide (≥99.8 %) was purchased from Merck KGaA, aqueous ammonia solution (≥25 %, extra pure) was purchased from Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG, acetonitrile (≤99.9 %) was purchased from Fisher Scientific and used without further purification. (NH₄)₂[Mo₃S₁₃] and Na₂[Mo₃S₁₃] were synthesized as described below. Water was either deionized prior to use or Milli-Q water was used after degassing for 24 h with argon.

Instruments:

Hydrogen evolution was quantified using a Bruker Scion SQ GC/MS, *Shimadzu Nexis GC-2030* or a Agilent Technologies 7820A GC-TCD by injecting manually 100 μL of the head space. Sample preparation under inert conditions was performed in an MBRAUN LABSTAR glovebox or under Ar flow, and the modular photoreactor was equipped with LZ1-00DB00 Dental Blue (λ = 460 nm), LST1-01F06-RYL1-00 Deep Blue (λ = 455 nm), or LZ4-00B208-0000 (λ = 453 nm) LED emitters to carry out photocatalytic experiments.

Experimental Setups

Photocatalytic experiments were carried out in the modular, 3D printed photoreactor. For the case studies irradiation chambers with the dimensions of 90x90x100 mm and 90x90x140 mm were used. The photoreactor was manufactured from polylactic acid using Fused Deposition Modelling. Due to its reflecting properties in the visible spectral range, white filament (Raise 3D premium) was used. The irradiation chamber of the reactor consists of two walls with slots (see Figure 1), in which sample holders can be installed. Circularly arranged vials can be irradiated from the bottom with an irradiation module at a defined (adjustable) distance from the light source. 4-vial (circular diameter = 24.0 mm) or 8-vial sample holder (circular diameter = 46.4 mm) were used to perform photocatalytic hydrogen evolution catalysis. Therefore 2 or 8 GC vials (4 or 8 mL) were placed in the 4- or 8-vial sample holder. The holder was placed at a distance of 70 mm from the vials and 100 mm for 8 mL GC-vials from the irradiation module. For irradiation 453 nm, 455 nm and 460 nm LEDs were used (see Table 1). The reaction chamber was ventilated using a fan (26 L s⁻¹) to avoid heating of the reaction chamber.

All CAD drawings of the modular reactor platform, assembly descriptions and the Python code for the controller are available on GitHub <https://github.com/photonZfeed/modularPhotoreactor> and as a stable version in the Zenodo repository <https://doi.org/10.5281/10.5281/zenodo.5615742>. Raw data of the

characterization can be found on Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/10.5281/10.5281/zenodo.5614942> and evaluated with the tools published on GitHub.^[1-3]

Figure 1: Photoreactor used for case studies. **a** top view of reactor, **b** corpus of reactor with **c** irradiation module.

Characterized LEDs

Table 1: Characterized LED and product numbers.

LED	Manufacturer	Product Number
365 nm	New Energy	LST1-01G01-UV01-00
385 nm	LED Engin	LZ1-00UB00-01U4
405 nm	LED Engin	LZ1-00UB00-01U7
405 nm	LED Engin	LZ1-V0UB0R-00U8
460 nm	LED Engin	LZ1-00DB00 Dental Blue
455 nm	New Energy	LST1-01F06-RYL1-00
453 nm	LED Engin	LZ4-40B208-0000
RGBA	LED Engin	LZ4-20MA00-0000
530 nm	New Energy	LST1-01F06-GRN1-00

Photocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution Catalysis

[Mo₃S₁₃] Catalyzed Hydrogen Evolution

Synthesis of (NH₄)₂[Mo₃S₁₃] x 2H₂O

The thiomolybdate (NH₄)₂[Mo₃S₁₃] x 2H₂O was prepared by a modification of the synthesis reported by Müller et al.^[4] (NH₄)₆[Mo₇O₂₄] x 4H₂O (4.0 g, 3.2 mmol) was dissolved in water (20 mL) in a round bottom flask, then ammonium polysulfide ((NH₄)₂S_x) solution (120 mL, 25 wt%) was added to it and fitted with a condenser. The solution was heated to 96 °C for five days without stirring. Dark-red crystals of (NH₄)₂[Mo₃S₁₃] x 2H₂O formed and were removed by filtration, washed with water, ethanol, carbon disulfide and ether. Finally, the product was air-dried. Yield: 5.6 g (7.16 mmol, 97.9% based on Mo).

Synthesis of Na₂[Mo₃S₁₃] x 5H₂O

Na₂[Mo₃S₁₃] x 5H₂O was synthesized according to literature. (NH₄)₂[Mo₃S₁₃] x 2H₂O (3.02 g, 3.86 mmol) was suspended in an aqueous NaOH solution (1 wt%, 40 mL) and stirred under reduced pressure (20 mbar) for 2 h, to remove ammonium as NH₃ gas. The resulting dark red solution was filtered into an aqueous NaCl solution (10 wt%, 100 mL). After 12 h, the precipitated product was isolated by filtration, washed with 2-propanol and diethyl ether, and dried in vacuo at room temperature to give red-brown powder of Na₂[Mo₃S₁₃] x 5H₂O. Yield: 3.20 g (3.78 mmol, 95.9% based on Mo).

Sample Preparation and Photocatalysis with Low Methanol Ratio

For the electron donor solution 708 or 528 mg of L-ascorbic acid were dissolved in 18 mL of degassed H₂O, then the pH was corrected, using a diluted solution of NH₄OH in a syringe, reaching a final pH of 6. Afterwards, the volume was adjusted to 20 mL of total volume by addition of degassed water, reaching an ascorbic acid concentration of 0.2 M and 0.15 M, respectively. The entire procedure was done under argon flow using a Schlenk line.

To obtain a methanol-water ratio of 1:1, an 8 mL GC vial with 4 mL of catalysis solution, composed of 1.2 mL of MeOH, 0.4 mL [Ru(bpy)₃(PF₆)₂] (200 μM), 2 mL ascorbic acid (0.2 M) and 0.4 mL Na₂[Mo₃S₁₃] x 5H₂O (3 μM), was prepared.

To obtain a methanol-water ratio of 1:2, an 8 mL GC vial with 3 mL of catalysis solution, composed of 0.4 mL of MeOH, 0.3 mL [Ru(bpy)₃(PF₆)₂] (200 μM), 2 mL ascorbic acid (0.15 M) and 0.3 mL Na₂[Mo₃S₁₃] x 5H₂O (3 μM), was prepared.

Sample preparation was done using a glovebox. The vial was then sealed, transferred into the photoreactor and irradiated by a LED emitter (λ = 460 nm) with a current of 0.7 A and voltage of 4.0 V. Simultaneously, 8 identically prepared vials were irradiated while stirring during 6 hours for each experiment.

Catalytic conditions: [catalyst] = 0.3 μM; [photosensitizer] = 20 μM; [Ascorbic Acid] = 100 mM; Solvent = MeOH/H₂O 1:1; 1:2 v:v

A minimal data set for the experiments is available as separate “[Mo3S13]_low_methanol.xlsx”-file as electronic supporting information.^[5]

Sample Preparation and Photocatalysis with High Methanol Ratio

A freshly prepared aqueous 1 M stock solution of ascorbic acid was adjusted to pH 4 using aqueous NH₃. To GC vials (5 mL) 200 μL of the ascorbic acid stock solution, 1747 μL of MeOH and 34.4 μL of a [Ru(bpy)₃](PF₆)₂ stock solution (1.1634 mM, 1 g/L in MeOH) was added and degassed with argon for 20 min. For each reaction trial a [Mo₃] stock solution was freshly prepared. Therefore, 1 mg of (NH₄)₂[(Mo₃S₁₃)] was dissolved in 1 mL DMF. After complete dissolution, 39 mL of MeOH were added, resulting in a final concentration of 32.18 μM (0.025 g/L). Under argon atmosphere, 18.64 μL of the [Mo₃] stock solution was added to the reaction vials and the rubber septum caps were exchanged by unused ones (avoiding loss of produced hydrogen by pierced septa). Irradiation was started within 1-2 min after adding the [Mo₃].

Catalytic conditions: [catalyst] = 0.3 μM; [photosensitizer] = 20 μM; [Ascorbic Acid] = 100 mM; Solvent = MeOH/H₂O 9:1 v:v

A minimal data set for the experiments is available as separate “[Mo3S13]_high_methanol.xlsx”-file as electronic supporting information.^[5]

Co(dm_g)₂ClPy Catalyzed Hydrogen Evolution

Sample Preparation and Photocatalysis

Solvents were deoxygenated by distillation under a N₂ atmosphere or bubbling with an Ar flow. For the preparation of each reaction vessel in the glovebox, a freshly prepared CH₃CN solution of [Co(dm_g)₂ClPy] (104 μL, 2.25 mM), a CH₃CN solution of *N,N*-Dimethyl-*p*-toluidine (DMT) (14 μL, 1.155 M), a CH₃CN solution of H₂O (24 μL, 0.276 M) and, a CH₃CN solution of [Ru(bpy)₃](PF₆)₂ (12 μL, 1.26 mM) were filled in a LABSOLUTE clear glass screw neck vial (ND13, total volume 5 mL), equipped with a magnetic stirrer, and filled with CH₃CN (2846 μL) to reach a 3 mL solution. Subsequently, the vials were sealed with a screw seal (ND13, butyl red / PTFE grey) and stored in the dark, until they were placed in the reactor holder and irradiated by a 450 nm LED for 30 minutes with a current of 0.2 A (or 0.4 A) and a voltage of 16 V under vigorous stirring.

Catalytic conditions: [catalyst] = 78 μM; [photosensitizer] = 5 μM; [DMT] = 5.5 mM; [H₂O] = 2.2 mM; solvent = CH₃CN.

A minimal data set for the experiments is available as separate “Co(dm_g)₂ClPy.xlsx”-file as electronic supporting information.^[5]

Photonic Characterization

Chemical Actinometry

For all actinometric experiments a corpus of the modular photoreactor with dimensions 90x90x100 mm printed with orange PLA (Raise 3D premium) was used. 1, 4 or 8 of the vials were fixed in a 1-vial, 4-vial (circular diameter = 24.0 mm) or 8-vial (circular diameter = 46.4 mm) sample holder and the holder was placed at a distance of 7 cm from the irradiation module.

To investigate the homogeneity of irradiation of the vials aligned circularly at a defined distance from the radiation source, 8 vials were exemplarily placed in the 8-vial sample holder in the corpus and irradiated with a 365 nm LED (LST1-01G01-UV01-00) at a constant current of 500 mA for 10 s, 120 s, and 240 s, respectively.

After irradiation all vials were probed immediately by diluting 1 mL of the actinometer solution with 19 mL 0.05 M H₂SO₄. 5 mL of the diluted actinometer solution were added to 15 mL developer solution (0.06 M CH₃COONa × 3 H₂O and 0.006 M 1,10-Phenantroline in 0.05 M H₂SO₄).^[6,7] The prepared solution was developed for 1 h. The absorbance of the developed solution was measured in a quartz cuvette (d = 1 cm) using a Biochrom WPA S800+ tabletop spectrometer at a wavelength of 510 nm.

Additionally, measurements with a higher time resolution were conducted with the same setup and procedure, where one after another vial was removed from the corpus for sampling every 20 s starting 100 s after the LED was switched on. During this period, irradiation with the LED was interrupted. After sampling, the sampled vial was refilled with fresh actinometer solution to the original volume of 3 mL and placed back in the corpus. The irradiation was continued for another 20 s. The procedure was repeated until all eight vials were sampled. The last sampled vial was thus irradiated for 240 s.

The same procedure was used to determine photon fluxes for the 4-vial sample holder equipped with 4 vials at 120 s, 160 s, 200 s and 240 s. For the 1-vial sample holder equipped with 1 vial, photon fluxes were determined at the same times as for the 4-vial sample holder.

Radiometry

For the measurements of all sole radiation sources, an area of 596.7 mm × 596.7 mm starting at the x/y-position (0.0 mm/0.0 mm) was scanned. For all measurements with the radiation source installed in the corpus, an area of 273.0 mm × 273.0 mm starting at the x/y-position (150.0 mm/180.0 mm) was scanned. The measured radiation source was placed at a distance of 166.0 mm from the entrance of the cosine corrector of the spectrometer. Routinely, four measurements were conducted: i) measurement of the radiation source, ii) measurement of the radiation source with 1-8 vials filled with 3 mL of 7.5 mM methyl orange solution placed in the beam path at a distance of 5, 7 and 9 cm, iii) measurement of the radiation source installed in the corpus and iv) measurement of the radiation source placed in the corpus with 1-8 empty vials placed in the beam path at a distance of 5, 7 and 9 cm. The incident radiant power of the radiation sources was then calculated from calibration.

Calibration of the Radiometric Setup for the 365 nm LED (LST1-01G01-UV01-00)

The measured data of the 2D radiometry scans taken at a constant current (365 nm LED, $I = 0.5$ A) were corrected with a calibration factor of 2.344 to the calibration curve shown in Figure 2. The calibration curve was acquired using a calibrated measurement setup consisting of an Avantes AvaSphere-50-IRRAD integrating sphere coupled with an Avantes FC-UVIR600-1-ME fiber optic cable (Presol) to an Avantes AvaSpec-ULS2048CL-RS-EVO spectrometer with a DCL-UV/VIS-200 detector collection lens and a Slit-25-

RS 25 μm slit. The measurement setup was calibrated using a Heraeus Noblelight Deuterium DO 650 TJ lamp and covers a wavelength range of 200-400 nm. A radiant power of 900 mW was measured, indicating only 2.9 % deviation from the technical specifications given in the technical datasheet (875 mW at a constant current of 0.5 A). Therefore, the calibrations for the 453 nm, 455 nm and 460 nm LED were performed according to the optical powers reported by the supplier.

Figure 2: Calibration for the 365 nm LED.

Figure 3: Uncalibrated radiometric result of the 2D scan of the 365 nm LED.

Calibration of the Radiometric Setup for the 455 nm LED (LST1-01F06-RYL1-00)

The measured data of the 2D radiometry scans taken at a constant current (455 nm LED, $I = 0.29$ A) were corrected with a calibration factor of 1.559 to the calibration curve shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Calibration of the 455 nm LED.

Figure 5: Uncalibrated radiometric result of the 2D scan of the 455 nm LED. **a** 290 mA, **b** 350 mA and **c** 700 mA.

Calibration of the Radiometric Setup for the 460 nm LED (LZ1-00DB00 Dental Blue)

The measured data of the 2D radiometry scans taken at a constant current (460 nm LED, $I = 0.7$ A) were corrected with a calibration factor of 1.565 to the calibration curve shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Calibration of the 460 nm LED.

Figure 7: Uncorrected radiometric result of the 2D scan of the 460 nm LED. **a** 700 mA, **b** 1000 mA.

Calibration of the Radiometric Setup for the 453 nm LED (LZ4-40B208-0000)

The measured data of the 2D radiometry scans taken at a constant current (453 nm LED, $I = 0.2$ A) were corrected with a calibration factor of 1.557, the measurements taken with a constant current of 0.4 A and 0.95 A were corrected with factors of 1.532 and 1.510, to the calibration curve shown in Figure 6.

Figure 9 : Calibration of the 453 nm LED.

Figure 8: Uncorrected radiometric result of the 2D scan of the 453 nm LED. **a** 200 mA, **b** 400 mA, **c** 700 mA, **d** 950 mA and **e** 1000 mA.

Determination of the absorbed photon flux

Photon fluxes measured radiometrically always represent the part of the radiation which is not blocked by an object located in the radiation path between the radiation source and the spectrometer. This applies to the measured photon fluxes q_a , q_b , q_c and q_d shown in Figure 12 **a**, **b**, **c** and **d** of the main document. Therefore, absorbed photon fluxes can be calculated radiometrically only subtractively. The procedure for the subtractive determination of the absorbed photon flux is crucial for the accuracy of the result.

Determination of the photon flux was conducted with 2D radiometric measurements with the following steps (exemplified for the 365 nm LED (LST1-01G01-UV01-00) operated at a constant current of 0.5 A):

- 1) **Determination of the photon flux emitted by the LED:** corresponding to the measurement of the sole radiation source (Figure 12 a), yielding the emitted photon flux of $2854 \text{ nmol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$.

$$q_{emitted} = q_a = 2854 \text{ nmol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \quad (1)$$

- 2) **Calculation of the photon flux absorbed by the entire setup:** By subtracting the photon flux of the measurement for the LED installed in the corpus equipped with methyl orange filled vials in the 8 vial holder (Figure 12 d) from the emitted photon flux (Figure 12 a). The result is a photon flux absorbed by the setup of $2387 \text{ nmol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$.

$$q_{emitted} - q_d = q_{setup} = 2387 \text{ nmol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \quad (2)$$

- 3) **Determination of the photon flux absorbed by the absorbing solution:** The following calculations consider that the photon flux measured with radiometry is always the photon flux remaining after light interacted with the experimental setup. Therefore, all ratios calculated in the following have to be subtracted from "1" (the emitted photons). For this purpose, the ratio of the photon fluxes of measurement **c** and **b** is calculated. This represents the fraction of the photon flux absorbed by the holder ($x_1 = 0.176$). The ratio of **d** and **b** reflects the fraction of the photon flux absorbed by the absorbing solution and the holder ($x_2 = 0.483$). The fraction of the photon flux absorbed by the absorbing solution is obtained by subtracting the fraction absorbed by the holder (x_1) from the fraction absorbed by the holder and the solution (x_2). Thus, the fraction of the photon flux absorbed by the solution x_3 is 0.307. Multiplication with the total photon flux absorbed by the setup yields the photon flux absorbed by the solution as $q_{tot} = 733 \text{ nmol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. The photon flux per vial $q_{vial} = 92 \text{ nmol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ can be calculated dividing q_{tot} by the total number of irradiated vials N_{vial} .

$$1 - \frac{q_c}{q_b} = x_1 = 0.176 \quad (3)$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{q_d}{q_b}\right) x_2 = 0.483 \quad (4)$$

$$x_2 - x_1 = \frac{q_c - q_d}{q_b} = x_3 = 0.307 \quad (5)$$

$$q_{\text{setup}} \cdot x_3 = 2387 \text{ nmol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot 0.307 = q_{\text{tot}} = 733 \text{ nmol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \quad (6)$$

Figure 10: Photon flux absorbed per vial (left) and total photon flux (right) for different holders.

$$q_{\text{vial}} = \frac{q_{\text{tot}}}{N_{\text{vial}}} = 92 \text{ nmol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \quad (7)$$

Figure 11: Radiometric scans for the setup with 1-vial and 4-vial holder. For the reference measurements of the sole and corpus mounted 365 nm LED see Figure 9 a and b. **a** 1-vial-setup with empty vial, **b** 1-vial setup filled with absorbing solution, **c** 4-vials setup with empty vials, **d** 4-vial setup with vials filled with absorbing solution.

Figure 13: Absorbed volumetric photon flux for different holders and a fully absorbing methyl orange solution.

Figure 12: Photonic efficiencies per vial (left) and in total (right) for different vial holders

Figure 15: Radiometric scans for a vertical position of 5 and 9 cm with the 8-vial holder. For the reference measurements of the sole and corpus mounted 365 nm LED see Figure 9 a and b. a empty vials at vertical position 5, b vials filled with absorbing solution at vertical position 5, c empty vials at vertical position 9, d vials filled with absorbing solution at vertical position 9.

Figure 14: Volumetric photon flux (left) and total photonic efficiency (right) for different vertical positions of the vials relative to the radiation source.

Photon Fluxes for the Experimental Setups used for Case Studies

Figure 16: Case studies 700 mA (LZ1-00DB00 Dental Blue). **a** 460 nm module, **b** LED module installed in the corpus, **c** 8-vial setup with empty vials at vertical position 7, **d** 8-vials-setup with vials filled with absorbing solution at vertical position 7.

Figure 17 Case studies 290 mA (LST1-01F06-RYL1-00). **a** 455 nm LED module, **b** LED module installed in the corpus, **c** 8-vial setup with empty vials at vertical position 7, **d** 8-vials-setup with vials filled with absorbing solution at vertical position 7.

Figure 19: Case studies 200 mA (LZ4-40B208-0000). **a** 453 nm LED module, **b** LED module installed in the corpus, **c** 8-vial setup with empty vials at vertical position 7, **d** 8-vials-setup with vials filled with absorbing solution at vertical position 7, **e** 2-vials setup with empty vials at vertical position 7, **f** 2-vials setup with vials filled with absorbing solution at vertical position 7.

Figure 18: Case studies 400 mA (LZ4-40B208-0000). **a** 453 nm LED module, **b** LED module installed in the corpus, **c** 2-vial setup with empty vials at vertical position 7, **d** 2-vials-setup with vials filled with absorbing solution at vertical position 7.

Figure 20: Case studies 950 mA (LZ4-40B208-0000). **a** 453 nm module, **b** LED module installed in the corpus, **c** 8-vial setup with empty vials at vertical position 7, **d** 8-vials-setup with vials filled with absorbing solution at vertical position 7.

Wavelength Dependent Reflective Properties of the Reactor Material

Three 3D printed reflective samples made of PLA (Raise 3D premium) colored in white, black and orange were tested for their reflectivity properties in comparison to a mirror reference using an integrating sphere made of optical PTFE with an inner diameter of 15 cm. The reflective samples were irradiated with a fiber-coupled Energetiq EQ-99X-FC plasma light source. The light source was connected to the integrating sphere by a Avantes FC-UV600-1-ME-SR fiber optic cable, and the reflection samples were irradiated at an angle of 7° . An Avantes Avaspec-ULS2048CL-EVO-RS 02/17 spectrometer with a $200 \mu\text{m}$ slit Slit-200-RS coupled to the integrating sphere with a Avantes FC-UVIR600-2-ME-SMA/FC fiber optic cable was used for the measurements. The used setup is shown in Figure 21. The relative total reflectance of the reflectance samples was calculated from the ratio of counts between the respective sample to the mirror reference registered by the spectrometer.

The results of the measurements are depicted in Figure 22. All filaments show a low reflectivity of about 20 % for a wavelength below 370 nm. Between 350 - 490 nm, the reflectivity of the white PLA increases to about 90 % and remains at this value over the entire visible range. A similar behavior can be observed for the orange PLA in a wavelength range of 470 – 590 nm. Reflectivity increases up to about 73 %, where it reaches a maximum and drops continuously to about 68 % up to a wavelength of 750 nm. The black PLA has a low reflectivity of less than 10 % over the entire visible wavelength range. Colored reactor materials should be chosen with care and adjusted to the requirements of the setup.

Figure 22: **a** Reflection samples and measurement setup, **b** optical fiber (out) to spectrometer connection, **c** reflection sample (white) and **d** optical fiber (in) from plasma light source.

Figure 21: Wavelength dependent relative reflectance of white, orange and black PLA (Raise 3D premium).

- [1] M. Sender, D. Ziegenbalg, “multiDradiometry,” DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4898137 <https://github.com/photonZfeed/multiDradiometry>, **2021**.
- [2] M. Sender, B. Wriedt, D. Ziegenbalg, *React. Chem. Eng.* **2021**, *6*, 1601–1613.
- [3] M. Sender, D. Ziegenbalg, *React. Chem. Eng.* **2021**, *6*, 1614–1627.
- [4] A. Müller, S. Pohl, M. Dartmann, J. P. Cohen, J. M. Bennett, R. M. Kirchner, *Zeitschrift für Naturforsch. B* **1979**, *34*, 434–436.
- [5] D. Ziegenbalg, A. Pannwitz, S. Rau, B. Dietzek-Ivanšić, C. Streb, **2021**, DOI 10.5281/zenodo.5575037.
- [6] B. Wriedt, D. Ziegenbalg, *ChemPhotoChem* **2021**, cptc.202100122.
- [7] B. Wriedt, D. Ziegenbalg, *J. Flow Chem.* **2020**, *10*, 295–306.